

Социокультурное значение подготовки кадров по физической культуре и спорту в системе высшего образования

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение. Актуальность исследования заключается в характеристике трансформации высшего образования, вызванной стремительным развитием многополярности как новой геополитической модели мира, определяющей стратегические направления социокультурного значения подготовки кадров по физической культуре и спорту в образовательных учреждениях высшего образования.

Целью исследования является выявление социокультурного значения образовательного процесса подготовки кадров по физической культуре и спорту в высшем образовании.

Материалы и методы. Материалы исследования: научные статьи (платформы: eLIBRARY.RU, Scopus, Web of Science); информация и аналитические материалы на основе результатов мониторинга деятельности высших учебных заведений физической культуры и спорта России.

Результаты исследования. В рамках данного исследования выявлены структурные особенности и сформулировано понятие социокультурного значения подготовки кадров по физической культуре и спорту в системе высшего образования. Полученные результаты исследования являются значимыми для углубленного понимания сущности социокультурного значения подготовки кадров по физической культуре и спорту в системе высшего образования, позволяют выделить его инвариантные компоненты и обеспечивают целостность процесса, а также осуществить прогностические оценки данных, приоритеты кадровой политики, повышения качества жизни, сохранения и укрепления здоровья населения, роста человеческого капитала.

Заключение. Проведенное исследование позволило сформулировать понятие социокультурного значения подготовки кадров по физической культуре и спорту в системе высшего образования, которое является производной от совокупности уровневых актуальных компонентов социокультурного вектора глобальных состояний; социокультурных функций высшей школы в пространстве диалога культур; физкультурно-спортивной отрасли; национальных стратегических векторов развития отрасли; профессиональных стандартов в сфере физической культуры и спорта; региональных особенностей системы физической культуры и спорта; факторов социального, гражданского и профессионального становления личности.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

социокультурная среда, социокультурное пространство, подготовка кадров, физическая культура и спорт, высшее образование, профессиональная подготовка

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Лицензия «С указанием авторства — С сохранением условий». Позволяет перерабатывать, исправлять и развивать произведения при условии указания авторства и лицензирования производных работ на аналогичных условиях.

Sociocultural significance of training in physical education and sport in the system of higher education

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of the study is to characterize the transformation of higher education caused by the rapid development of multipolarity as a new geopolitical model of the world, which determines the strategic directions of the sociocultural significance of personnel training in physical culture and sport in educational institutions of higher education in our country.

The aim of the study is to identify the sociocultural significance of the educational process of training personnel in physical culture and sport in higher education.

Materials and methods. Research materials: scientific articles (platforms: eLIBRARY.RU, Scopus, Web of Science); information and analytical materials based on the results of monitoring the activities of higher education institutions of physical culture and sport in Russia.

Results. Within the framework of this study the structural features were revealed and the concept of sociocultural significance of training in physical culture and sport in the system of higher education was formulated. The obtained results of the study are significant for an in-depth understanding of the essence of the sociocultural significance of personnel training in physical culture and sport in the system of higher education, allow us to identify its invariant components and ensure the integrity of the process, carry out predictive assessments of the data, as well as priorities of personnel policy, improving the quality of life, preserving and strengthening the health of the population, human capital growth.

Conclusion. The conducted research allowed us to formulate the concept of sociocultural significance of personnel training in physical culture and sport in the system of higher education, which is derived from a set of level relevant components of the sociocultural vector of global states; sociocultural functions of higher education in the space of dialogue of cultures; physical culture and sport industry; national strategic vectors of industry development; professional standards in the field of physical culture and sport; regional peculiarities of the system of higher education.

KEYWORDS

sociocultural environment, sociocultural space, training, physical education and sport, higher education, professional training

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INTRODUCTION

Education as a socio-cultural phenomenon determines all spheres of society and experiences a certain reverse influence. Multipolarity, as a new geopolitical global model of the world, determines the strategic directions of socio-cultural importance of personnel training in educational institutions of higher education in our country, and special attention is also paid to the preservation and strengthening of public health.

The socio-cultural significance of higher education is declared by documents of international organizations UNESCO, the United Nations. It should be noted that the United Nations Declaration on Human Rights Education and Training states that "the World Programme for Human Rights Education and specific national and local needs and priorities should be taken into account" [1, p. 8]. UNESCO's activities to stimulate transformations in the field of education for sustainable development until 2030, it is defined within the framework of an ambitious Action Framework [2].

Currently, a number of international intergovernmental organizations are active in the field of higher education. The most significant of them is the World Bank. The impact of the World Bank on the modernization of the education system is described in the article by D. B. Edwards et al. [3]. The International Association of Universities (IAU) has developed a Strategy for the International Association of Universities (2022-2030) [4].

Structural and substantive changes in the field of "Physical Culture and Sports" impose requirements for the possession of fundamentally new professional competencies by specialists. This category of specialists is responsible for prioritizing the formation of the foundations of a healthy lifestyle, and therefore training in the field of physical culture is a key factor in the health of the population.

The study of the socio-cultural specifics of education and structural changes in the higher education system as a social institution is especially relevant in the context of geopolitical global changes in the world, multipolarity. The relevance of the research is due to modern requirements for the readiness of higher educational institutions to develop and implement basic professional educational programs of higher education (hereinafter - the BPEP of HE) in accordance with socio-cultural actors, relevant professional standards and the labor functions contained therein; regional peculiarities of the system of physical culture and sports; factors of social, civic and professional formation of personality.

The purpose of the study is to identify the socio-cultural significance of the educational process of training in physical culture and sports in higher education.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In foreign and domestic science, the identification of the socio-cultural significance of the educational process of training in physical culture and sports in higher education remains insufficiently studied. For a comprehensive analysis of specific opportunities to ensure the modernization of higher education, methodological developments of the conceptual and political reinterpretation of the term «education» by N. Almeida-Filho [5]; dynamism of the socio-cultural process by A. P. Gorbunov [6]; actor-network theory; conceptual model of internal quality assurance of higher education by M. Krooi and co-authors [7] were used. To achieve this goal, a critical analysis of scientific publications of foreign and Russian specialists over the past five years has been carried out (platforms: eLibrary.ru, Scopus, Web of Science), as well as information and analytical materials based on the results of monitoring the activities of educational institutions of higher education of Russian universities of physical culture and sports.

The research methods are comparison, concretization, systematic and comparative analysis.

THE RESULTS OF THE STUDY

For many developed countries, critical and creative forecasting is essential in order to identify the socio-cultural significance of higher education and its prospects. Transformational trends in higher education are responsible for the broad values of sustainable development; they reflect economic and socio-political trends.

The priority importance of higher education in the socio-cultural planetary aspect is noted by N. Almeida-Filho [5]. The author introduces the concept of «ecosocial sensitivity», which notes, on the one hand, planetary consciousness and systemic responsibility, on the other hand, openness to change and transepistemic thinking.

The dynamism of the socio-cultural process of transformative and creative formation of the parameters of the future Russia determines the prospects of the higher education system. The fundamentally sound projected parameters of Russia as a carrier of a sovereign-sovereign Russian higher school, the data obtained by us, are consistent with the opinion presented in the study by A. P. Gorbunov [6]. The author identifies the criteria for the transformative and creative formation of the parameters of the future Russia as a leader-co-integrator power. This defines it as the most advanced civilizational and formational type of society and state. Considering the design on a perspective-oriented basis in accordance with the key parameters of Russian higher school systems, the author concludes the prospects and viability in this area. The importance of a comprehensively connected approach is noted, which defines pragmatic and logical connectives, connectedness, all-connectedness and guarantees the unity and integrity of all analysis and design, all conclusions and generalizations achieved.

M. Krooi and co-authors presented a conceptual model of internal quality assurance in higher education, which promotes a contextualized and integrated approach to internal quality assurance [7].

Considering the dynamism of the socio-cultural process, we will analyze the connection between the ontology of network theory and the study of socio-political relations. Actor-network theory focuses on determining the diversity and dynamics of the structure, as well as the characteristics of the actor and his place in the structure of relations with other actors. This topic has been developed by many scientists (O. M. Mikhaylenok, A. V. Brega, G. A. Malysheva, etc.) [8]. Researchers have found that each actor can change existing relationships, but the ability to act is not his internal resource, but an acquisition during interaction with other acting actors. Therefore, the actor is never the only source of action; his actions are always approved by other actors. This leads to the main thesis of actor theory: a network in which each actor has its own network [8, p. 139].

A large stratum of sociocultural significance of higher education in different aspects is presented in the works of authors who have researched this problem.

We agree with the scientists who analyze the socio-cultural functions of higher education in the space of cultural dialogue as a component of the socio-cultural process. Thus, F. Martorane and co-authors believe that the theoretical principles and practical goals that underlie multiculturalism and interculturalism complement each other. At the same time, they focus on different levels, according to the researchers. Multiculturalism is at the macro level, while interculturalism is more focused on the meso- and micro-levels [9]. L. Wong and co-authors investigated the features of the introduction of mobile marketing in social networks in the context of digital technologies using an expanded model of the adoption of mobile technologies in the higher education system. At the same time, the properties of network relations and social influence on the spread of innovations were studied [10]. L. M. McDougale and co-authors justified service education in higher education institutions and the formation of a prosocial identity [11]. A. Al-Khatib Dilek and Y. Kagnici identified the impact of the cultural adaptation program on the adaptation of foreign students. As part of this study, a psychoeducation program based on multicultural competencies and Berry's acculturation model was developed to improve the adaptation process of international students. The quantitative results of the study showed that the cultural adaptation program significantly influenced the personal and social adaptation of foreign students. However, it did not have a significant impact on adaptation to the university environment, emotional adaptation, relationship relationships and academic adaptation [12].

Russian sociocultural reformation is a Socioproject, which is analysed in the study by Y. M. Osipov [13]. The author, based on a deep scientific analysis, reveals "what expresses the state and cultural independence, autonomy of the transformation process" [13, p. 213]. At the same time, the depth of the influence of external international factors with not only constructive but also negative components is noted. Consequently, the world-conditioned process that tends "to mono-ethatism, more and more opposed to the traditionally existing poly-ethatism (in qualitative assessment)" [13, p. 214], does not allow self-identification. The author concludes that one of the ways to maintain the diversity of the global unification process is regional integration on the basis of "high national-state self-consciousness" [13, p. 215]. In the course of scientific research it is substantiated that any reform project involves a conceptual choice. In this case, ten conceptual principles are distinguished: sociality, civilisationality, statehood, patriotism, internationality, humanity, environmental friendliness, cost-effectiveness, industriality, spirituality.

The data obtained by us are consistent with the authors' opinion on the implementation of humanitarian expertise in education, which determine the dynamism of the sociocultural process. Among them we should note the theory of planetary social pedagogy, reflecting the perspectives of the sociocultural process (A.O. Salonen et al.) [14]. The study by T. I. Grabelnykh et al. clarifies the concepts of sociocultural space and sociocultural environment of higher education institution; formulates the goals and objectives of humanitarian expertise in education; presents the technology of its implementation; reflects the stages, outlines the methods that determine the order of work at each of them [15]. The obtained scientific data have applied significance for substantiating the sociocultural importance of personnel training in physical education and sport in the system of higher education.

The analysis of crisis phenomena in education and ways to overcome them, which determine the dynamism of the sociocultural process, identified in our study, is consistent with the opinions of K. R. Bayanov and N. P. Pavlova [16]. Scientists claim the introduction of the Bologna system as a particularly significant cause of the destruction of the Russian system of higher education. An important factor of the education crisis is the change in the goals of the activities of the participants of the educational process, deontologisation of a person. The relevance of revision of the main vector, which is given to the educational reforms, is noted. In our opinion, the socio-cultural understanding and direction of this process is important for overcoming the crisis.

Of interest are philosophical and cultural studies of the socio-cultural specifics of education and structural changes in the education system as a social institution, which are presented in a multifaceted way in scientific research. Firstly, they point out the imbalance of the goals declared by the reformers and the implemented tasks, the most vulnerable places of further actual and radical directions of modernisation of educational activity; positive and negative positions of this process, hidden and potential possibilities of its modification are revealed (M. U. Tran) [17]. Secondly, a harmonious and sociocultural vision of social and humanistic learning that awakens learning, society, culture and people, provides a unique experience of unity, free, non-linear, independently designed and structured system of interaction. The main objective is to change the socio-cultural environment, whether to consider external effects, to design a social-humanistic educational system or to practice motivational power. This process aims to create an open sociocultural educational space (K. Lars) [18]. Third, autonomy-supportive learning: its flexibility, benefits and potential for improving educational practice (J. Reeve, S. H. Cheon) [19].

Fourthly, higher education is a factor of social, civic and professional formation of personality as a condition for the development of soft skills in a sustainable society (M. Sá, S. Serpa) [20].

The sociocultural dynamism of the process of modernisation of higher education is particularly affected by digitalisation. The peculiarities of the modern social situation are conditioned by the formation of information society and the development of information and communication technologies. The inevitable actual vector is the informatisation of the world space, affecting all spheres of life both society as a whole and individual industries. The study and assessment of opportunities arising from the processes of digitalisation, as well as contradictions and risks in the field of digitalisation of such a complex ecosystem as the sphere of education, substantiated the socio-cultural unity and integrity of the three missions of the classical university – education, research and upbringing. In this case, we should agree with the results of the study by Y. Rohaila and co-authors, which examines digital socialization: changing value orientations of young people

regarding Internet use [21], as well as aspects of socio-cultural and psychological adaptation of students as intercultural communication, presented in the article by C. F. Hsu and J. Chen [22].

The digital transformation of higher education has a special role, which provides an important vector of the socio-cultural significance of higher education. Discussion articles on this issue reflect many issues of this process. Thus, the study by M.W. Johnson and co-authors notes digitalization and uncertainty at the university. Scientists have identified problems related to the adaptation of education to an increasingly complex post-digital environment, and also proposed methods of implementation research for transforming curricula, teaching and learning, based on the concept of uncertainty [23]. Considering possible risks and uncertainties in the process of digitalization of higher education, I. Zakharova and co-authors orient the educational technologies of the future to certain designs of five globally used learning management systems [24]. The results of the study by I. Langseth and co-authors also confirm previous studies indicating that a model of digital maturity and innovation should be developed in the emerging social field of digital transformation in higher education institutions [25]. Current trends in the development of neural network research in education are substantiated in the article by R. Hashem and co-authors [26]. The factors of cybersocialization and digital literacy of support staff [27], distance learning [28], work skills in the future educational space [29], digital competencies of teachers and students determine the current situation in education [30].

One of the directions of socio-cultural modernisation is the forecasting of new professions. The allocation of new professions as an imperative for the modernisation of the higher education system is a timely systematic process that meets modern development trends and needs. It is expected that in the future the project can be used in the process of developing new qualification requirements for in-demand professions, as well as be the basis for the development of basic professional training programmes for new professions. Modernisation of higher education in the process of interstate integration determines the specifics of education and structural changes in the education system [31]. The influence of artificial intelligence on the structure of demand for qualified personnel also determines the prospects of sociocultural significance of higher education [32].

In the context of global challenges, the sustainability of regional development is a priority for the state. The strategic academic leadership program «Priority 2030» is vectorially oriented towards sustainable socio-cultural and socio-economic development of the regions. The data obtained by us contain the main directions of the integration of universities as a driver of the development of science, culture, education and technology in the regions. They are consistent with the opinion of other authors [33]. The generalization and systematization of modern concepts and justifications of the approach to assessing the participation of universities in the socio-economic development of regions in Russia and abroad are focused on the future. Thus, the critical analysis and systematization of the research results of domestic and foreign authors allowed scientists to identify five main functions in justifying the role of universities in the socio-economic development of regions: the development of the innovation system and its elements, the socio-cultural role of the university, the university as a driver of regional development, training and employment of qualified personnel for the region, the university as an integrator of communications and interests (D. R. Gareeva, A. G. Shelomentsev) [34]. Let us consider these functions. The regional component in the content of education: socio-pedagogical approaches are presented in the scientific work of N. K. Gabdrakhmanov and co-authors [35]. The development of sports acts as a reflection of the socio-economic situation of the regions. Strategic resources of involvement the population in physical culture and sports activities determine the requirements and trends of the progressive development of vocational education in justifying the role of universities in the socio-economic development of regions, which is reflected in the publication of T.V. Skoblikova [36]. The principles of regionalisation, value orientations of modern higher education are conditioned by the basic definition of the regional component in the content of education to comprehend the prospects of its implementation in the practice of education.

The analysis allows us to substantiate the sociocultural significance of the educational process of training personnel in physical culture and sport in higher education. In the branch "Physical Culture and Sports" in accordance with the changing conditions and requirements of its development and modernisation actualize types of professional activities, labour functions. The modern list of professional standards that define the activities of specialists in the field of physical culture and sport on the basis of detailed labour functions substantiates the vectors of correction of the development

of the BPEP of HE. Currently, there are eighteen such professional standards for the branch "Physical Culture and Sport". The specifics of professional activity in the field of physical culture and sport are changing and require specialists to have special professional competences.

Numerous scientific studies testify to the complexity of the system of regulation of modernization of basic professional educational programmes in order to form in students professionally significant knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for effective performance of labour functions in the sphere of physical culture and sport in modern conditions, which agrees with the results of our study. Management of sports-pedagogical education: sociocultural orientation of the study is substantiated in the article by E. A. Popova co-authors [37]. Theoretical-retrospective and historical-contextual analyses of the formation and development of professional education in the aspect of human motor activity are structured in the publications by A. A. Gorelov co-authors. The research presents the results of retrospective analysis of physical education in our country in the dynamics over a 40-year period. The conducted research shows the importance of continuity of the system of personnel training for the physical culture and sports industry, the effectiveness of professional training is determined by the necessary and sufficient amount of time determined for certain blocks of professional training. Among which the following are highlighted: historical and humanitarian; psychological and pedagogical; medical and biological, theoretical and methodological; practical. An important aspect of the conducted research is the revealed sequence of mastering disciplines and their continuity [38].

Similar conclusions are presented in other scientific studies. Thus, investigating the features of integration of educational, scientific and sporting activities of students at different levels of professional education at the university of physical education, S. I. Petrov et al. revealed that the prerequisite for successful training at the second level is the balance of these activities at the first level. The quality of training competitive personnel for the physical culture and sports industry determines the degree, sequence, and the ratio of priority in the integration of educational, scientific and sports activities of students of a physical culture university [39].

These provisions of the conducted scientific analysis testify to the mandatory professional training of personnel at the Bachelor's degree level in physical education and sports orientation before training in the Master's programme in this direction of training. Unfortunately, for a number of years the persons who have a Bachelor's degree in any direction of training had the right to enter the Master's programme in physical culture and sports orientation. In this connection, the lack of basic necessary knowledge on the above mentioned blocks of professional training, and also insignificant quantity of time of training in magistracy, does not provide qualitative professional education to graduates. We consider it important in the reorganisation of higher education for the physical culture and sports industry as a prerequisite to provide the first level of higher education under this direction of training.

The next aspect of the socio-cultural significance of training in physical culture and sport in the system of higher education is the creation of a system for monitoring and forecasting the demand for specialists in the field of physical culture and sport both at the regional level and in the Russian Federation as a whole. A comprehensive analysis of the dynamics of state federal statistics data in the sphere of physical culture and sport is carried out by many scientists. The conducted research has allowed to identify regional peculiarities of staffing, to carry out prognostic assessments of data, as well as priorities of personnel policy.

An important factor in the socio-cultural significance of training in physical culture and sport is the expansion of the sports youth and adaptive movement. It should be noted the active construction of new sports facilities, an increase in the number of people involved in sports. At the same time there is a situation of low labour remuneration, poor social security of physical education specialists, their low social status. In order to harmonise the process, it is important to prioritise human resources policy and modernise basic professional education programmes accordingly.

The sociocultural significance of training in physical culture and sport determines the employment of graduates as an indicator of successful integration of sports work into the activities of universities of physical culture orientation. This aspect is presented in numerous scientific works. S. I. Petrov has conducted an extensive study of graduate employment in different perspectives. On the one hand, in the integral system of training specialists for the physical culture and sports industry;

on the other hand, in the regional context. The scientist revealed that there are specific features of graduate employment, which are determined by the location of the educational organisation of higher education, as well as the number of cultivated sports and their popularity in the region. The generalisation of the obtained data showed that graduates of the central higher education institutions of physical culture and sports orientation are more often employed in their field of activity. Apparently, it is connected with greater opportunities in the variety of sports represented in metropolitan regions. The development of sports can be considered as a reflection of the socio-economic situation of the regions [40].

L. I. Lubysheva and co-authors, considering the new contours of the development of higher professional education in the field of physical culture and sport, reasonably systematised the components of the sociocultural space of professional training [41]. Based on the results of monitoring the activities of educational organisations of higher education of Russian universities of physical culture and sport, the current trends in the development of theory and practice of personnel training on the basis of modern principles of building a system of professional education in this industry have been identified. As the next contour, let us consider the comprehension of the fundamental and practice-oriented nature of higher education in the process of socio-cultural transformations arising in real practice, which are characterized by non-linearity development of the educational system. Consequently, based on the consideration of praxiological knowledge to ensure the success of pedagogical actions, it is deeply significant to ensure disciplinary flexibility, reflexive reflection on the results of activity (D. A. Tomasova, A. P. Glukhov) [42].

Considering the forecast of staffing for achieving the target indicator of the Strategy for the Development of Physical Culture and Sports in the Russian Federation for the period until 2030, which ensures the readiness of specialists for new requirements and conditions of functioning of the physical culture and sports industry, we note the formation of profile types of labour activity, improvement of psychological and pedagogical support of training and competitive activity of athletes, high level of flexibility and social mobility through the prism of their educational trajectories.

Monitoring of the study of value orientations of representatives of various social groups, assessment of athletes' perception of external factors affecting training and competition activities, determines the next contour of the development of higher professional education in the field of physical culture and sport. In the publications devoted to various aspects of the issue under consideration, published over the last few years, significant is the study of T. V. Fanenshtil and E. V. Chibir, which considers the axiological aspect in the context of its significance for a person, for the implementation of the needs of goals, ideals [43]. In the article by F.M. Champ et al., existential and cultural-psychological approaches to understanding athlete identity are considered and strategies for developing well-rounded, reflective and self-aware athletes are proposed [44]. In the work prepared by J. Ribeiro et al. substantiate the ideas and principles of modern pedagogical models, including non-linear pedagogy and models of sportsmanship, including innovative ways of developing sports talents [45].

The conducted complex analysis of special scientific literature allows us to identify the main contours of higher education modernisation in the perspective, focused on the search for national priorities with an orientation on globalist trends, while an important condition for the development of higher professional education in the field of physical culture and sport is its socio-cultural significance.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The analysis conducted provides a basis for the sociocultural significance of the educational process in training physical culture and sports personnel in higher education. Competency, communicative, and sociocultural approaches, along with different conceptual perspectives on developing a modern structured educational process in higher education, enable a comprehensive approach to personnel training at the university. Our findings align with the results presented by other authors [5; 37].

Our analysis of the functioning of the higher education system reveals a redistribution of intellectual potential within the framework of the multipolar world paradigm. This paradigm underpins the civilizational paradigm of humanity, a finding consistent with the results of other researchers [18; 26]. The methodological basis is the synthesis of structural-functional and sociocultural approaches of Russian cultural studies. This allowed us to employ deconstruction as a key instrumental method, integrating known facts and meanings into a new context, aligning with the data of other authors [22; 38]. Therefore, within the current contextual dialogue of cultures, framed by the multipolar paradigm of the sociocultural development of higher education, a process of interrelation unfolds between key system-forming elements and the principles of deconstruction of higher education. Our findings align with the opinions of other scholars [18; 45]. These insights are crucial for the formation of a multipolar paradigm in the sociocultural development of higher education.

The principles of sociocultural significance in training physical culture and sports personnel within higher education should be grounded in a fundamental socio-political consensus and meet the following requirements: effective action and response, sustainability, and constructive adaptability. This aligns with the findings of the aforementioned authors [28; 36].

Therefore, when formulating the principles of sociocultural significance in training physical culture and sports personnel within higher education, it is advisable to draw upon actor-network theory. This entails acknowledging the actual micro- and macro-social ontological statuses of each object and the effects of their interactions. According to this theory, a plurality and heterogeneity of actants exist, whose essence is undefined until they interact with each other. This perspective aligns with the opinions of other scholars [8; 9]. In our research, the multifactorial nature of these interactions underpins the principles of sociocultural significance in training physical culture and sports personnel within the system of higher education.

A nation's strategic wealth lies in its young people: socially responsible, professionally trained, and harmoniously developed individuals. The system of higher education creates a unique oasis that meets the current demands and trends of the world, specifically in the training of competitive personnel. The formulated principles can serve as a guide for future research into this area. Moreover, these developed principles are crucial for the formation of a multipolar paradigm in the sociocultural development of higher physical education.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, our research enabled us to formulate the concept of sociocultural significance in training physical culture and sports personnel within higher education. This concept is derived from a set of multi-level current, tiered components: the sociocultural vector of global condition, the sociocultural functions of higher education within the space of cultural dialogue, the physical culture and sports industry, national strategic vectors of industry development, professional standards in physical culture and sports, regional specificities of the physical culture and sports system, and the sociocultural vector of higher education.

The study confirms the socio-cultural significance of higher education institutions' readiness to develop and implement core professional educational programs aligned with current professional standards and the labor functions outlined within them. Importantly, a balanced approach to these activities at the first level is a mandatory condition for successful personnel training at the second level. These findings from our scientific analysis underscore the necessity of mandatory professional training for personnel at the Bachelor's level in physical culture and sports before pursuing a Master's degree in this field. The research enabled us to identify regional peculiarities in staffing, conduct predictive assessments, and define priorities for personnel policy. The results of this study can be valuable for governmental agencies responsible for higher education strategy development, as well as for university leaders who plan target indicators for educational activities with a focus on socio-cultural aspects.

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